

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF FRP WITH BRAIDED STRUCTURE LATERAL COMPRESSIONAL BEHAVIORS OF GROUND TUBE

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ABSTRACT

This study deals with the braided composites tube and its mechanical properties. The surface of tubes used for golf shafts and mechanical parts which requires high dimensional accuracy are often grinded. In previous study, the lateral compressional behavior of tube with braided composites was clarified. Carbon fiber and epoxy resin were used as the reinforcement and matrix resin respectively; Tubular braided fabrics which changed the grind amount were made. And it was considered that the theoretical prediction using the curved beam theory is in agreement with the experimental results. The following results are obtained.

- It was suggested that the occurrence of breaking by the lateral compression was inter-laminar delamination regardless of the quantity of grind.
- It was suggested that maximum stress was high so that there is much quantity of abrasion, because maximum load does not change even in the increase of quantity of grind.
- It was suggested that there is no relationship between knee point and quantity of grind, because the occurrence of breaking by the lateral compression was the same.

1 INTRODUCTION

Braided fabrics are one of the typical textiles and have been expected to show an excellent performance as reinforcements for composite materials. Fig.1 shows the schematic drawing of braided fabrics. One of the important features is the continuity of fiber bundles which are oriented diagonally called braiding yarns (BY). They also have a capability of changing the orientation angles of braiding yarns called braiding angles. Another feature is that fiber bundles called middle end yarns (MEY) can be inserted into braiding yarns along the longitudinal direction, which makes excellent mechanical properties be expected. In addition, braided fabrics can be fabricated by using various kinds of fibers and MEY with different properties simultaneously.

This study deals with the braided composite tube and its mechanical properties. The surface of tubes that are used for golf shafts and mechanical parts with high dimensional accuracy are often grinded the surface. In previous study, the lateral compressional behavior of tube with braided composite was clarified. Carbon fibers and epoxy resin were used as the reinforcement and matrix

resin respectively; tubular braided fabrics with different amount of grinding were made in order to clarify.

And it was considered that the theoretical prediction using the curved beam theory is in agreement with the experimental results.

Fig.1. Structure of braided composites.

2 MATERIALS AND SPECIMEN FABRICATION

The tubular braided fabrics were fabricated by using carbon prepreg yarns with the filament number of 12000 (UTS50-12-RC38%-SX3 : JX Nippon Oil & Energy Corporation) Impregnated resin was modified epoxy resin of 35wt%. Type of material, number of filament, diameter of filament, tensile strength, young's modulus, tex and density are shown in Table.1.

The tubular braided fabrics of BY and MEY were fabricated by using the carbon fiber. One layer of braided fabrics was prepared on straight mandrel with 16 of BY and 8 of MEY. Braiding angle was 45 degree. The tubular braided fabrics of 4 layer structure were fabricated by using a straight mandrel ($\phi 12$) The inner 1st layer was used 16 of BY, the 2nd and 3rd layer were used 16 of BY and 8 of MEY. And 4th layer was used 16 of BY. Both 1st layer and 4th layer were used only BY, because the difference in the structure does not influence lateral compression. Each preforms were wrapped with PP tape with 15mm width cured in an oven at 130°C for 2hours. And Molded object was removed from the mandrel after fabrication.

Type of Material	Number of filament	Diameter of filament μm	Tensile strength Mpa	Young's modulus Gpa	Tex g/1000m	Density g/cm^3
UTS50-12K	12000	6.9	5100	245	800	1.8

Table 1 Properties of carbon fiber.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

4 kinds of specimens with different amount of grinding on the surface were changed were made. The grinding amount was decided by the diameter; no grinding, $\phi 16.4$, $\phi 16.3$ and $\phi 16.0$. The specimens were grinded with a numerical controlling machine, and the diameters of the specimens were measured using a non-contact laser sensor. Grind rate was amount of grind in 4th layer. Grind rate was calculated

Diameter	Wt.(g)	Length(mm)	Grind Wt.(g)	Grind Rate(%)
$\phi 16.0$	2.63	19.8	0.019	59.4
$\phi 16.3$	2.78	19.4	0.009	28.9
$\phi 16.4$	2.95	20.1	0.005	16.0
$\phi 16.6$	3.07	20.2	0.000	0.0

Table 2 Specification of specimen

4 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The grinding rate was calculated by Eq.(1). Fig.2 (a) shows the shape of the specimen. The inside diameter of the specimen is 16.0mm and the length is 20mm. The maximum outside diameter of both the laminated tube and the self-reinforced tube is 16.6. The specimen was placed between the upper and lower plate and was deformed by pushing down the upper plate, as shown in Fig.2(b). Lateral compressive tests were carried out by using the Instron Universal Machine at test speed of 2mm/min. Grinding rate is 0.0% (ϕ 16.6) , 16.0% (ϕ 16.4) , 28.9% (ϕ 16.3) , 59.4% (ϕ 16.0).

$$\text{Grinding ratio} = \frac{\text{Mass of the most outer layer} - \text{Mass of the ground most outer layer}}{\text{Mass of the most outer layer}} \quad (1)$$

Fig.2.(a) Dimension of specimen Fig.2.(b) Lateral compressive test

5 QUANTIFICATION

The theoretical prediction using the curved beam theory is in agreement with the experimental results. It is considered by the model of 1/4 of cylinder by symmetry as shown in Fig.3. W is compressive load, and R is diameter of cylinder.

$$M = M_0 + \frac{WR}{2}(1 - \cos \varphi) \quad (2)$$

$$M_0 = -\frac{WR}{2} \left(1 - \frac{2}{\pi}\right) \quad (3)$$

Since the maximum bending moment which occurs by the load point becomes the maximum at $\varphi=90^\circ$, M_{max} is calculated by Eq.(4)

$$M_{\max} = 0.318WR \quad (4)$$

Fig.3 Diagram of cylinder

Fig.4 Moment in cylinder

Maximum stress σ_{max} is found by calculating the distance between the center line and the neutral line. R is the diameter of the center line of the tube; R_1 is the diameter of the neutral line, and h is the distance from the cylinder section to the neutral line.

$$\sigma_{max} = \frac{M_{max}h}{Ae(R_1 - h)} \quad (5)$$

In the case where the beam is a rectangular section, the modulus of the section of curved beam α is calculated by Eq.(6) t is the thickness of the cylinder

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{t}{2R} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{5} \left(\frac{t}{2R} \right)^4 + \frac{1}{7} \left(\frac{h}{2R} \right)^6 \quad (6)$$

The distance e is calculated by Eq.(7)

$$e = \frac{R\alpha}{1+\alpha} \quad (7)$$

Fig.5 Diagram of curved beam

6 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Diameter	Grind Rate(%)	Maximum Stress (MPa)	Knee Point(MPa)	Maximum Load(N)
ϕ 16.0	59.4	450.3	90.0	340
ϕ 16.3	28.9	439.2	90.0	643
ϕ 16.4	16.0	435.2	90.0	663
ϕ 16.6	0.0	389.7	90.0	767

Table3. Compressive stress, knee point and load of tubular braided composites

The relationship of grinding rate and maximum stress, knee point, maximum load are shown in Table3. Even as the grinding rate increases, maximum load does not increase. Therefore the maximum stress has a tendency to become high when the grinding amount is big and the diameter is small .

Fig.6 Relationship between lateral compressive stress and strain

Fig.7 Relationship between maximum load and Grinding Rate

Fig.8 Relationship between Maximum Stress and Grinding Rate

Fig.9 Relationship between Equivalent Elastic Modulus and Grinding Rate.

The experimental value of the knee point did not change in spite of the grinding rate. The experimental value of the equivalent elastic modulus did not change in spite of the grinding rate as

well, because the diameter of the most outer layer became smaller by being grinded. The cause was considered by observing the sections of initial destruction and maximum load.

Cross-sectional photos at initial destruction and maximum load are showed in Fig.10-13. Initial destruction occurred in an inter-laminar delamination, and when more loads were continued, inter-laminar delamination was prolonged and generated destruction. None of the specimens were destructed in ground most outer layer.

Fig.10 Cross-sectional photos of grinding rate 0.0%

Fig.11 Cross-sectional photos of grinding rate 16.0%

Fig.12 Cross-sectional photos of grinding rate 28.9%

Fig13 Cross-sectional photos of grinding rate 59.4%

8 CONCLUSIONS

In sheet wrapping method, in order to get rid of the unevenness of the surface when overlapping fiber bundle to generate braided composites, the surface is often grinded. The influence on load and stress caused by grinding was examined.

- It was suggested that the occurrence of breaking by the lateral compression was inter-laminar delamination regardless of quantity of grind.
- It was suggested that higher the amount of abrasion is the higher the maximum stress becomes, because maximum load does not change even in an increase in the quantity of grind.
- It was suggested that there is no relationship between knee point and quantity of grind, because the occurrence of breaking by the lateral compression was the same. And the influence on shearing stress caused by grinding is considered by next study.

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